

Role of metal ions, EDTA and phosphatase enzyme during the solubilisation of Indian rock phosphate by *Aspergillus niger*

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Abstract : The process of solubilisation of rock phosphate by a mutant strain of *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ was stimulated by adding FeSO₄·7H₂O to the incubation medium. EDTA at a concentration of 30 mg/ml greatly enhanced the solubilisation process whereas CaCO₃ (0.5–2.0%) and ZnSO₄·7H₂O inhibited the process. Phosphatase activity and acid production was found to vary directly with the solubilisation process.

Keywords : Solubilisation, rock phosphate, mutant, phosphatase.

Introduction

Phosphorous is an essential plant nutrient, required for higher crop yields. Indian soils are generally poor in available phosphorus and thus a limiting factor in crop productivity¹. This deficiency is met by exogenous supply through phosphatic fertilizers². The raw materials for these fertilizers have to be imported. However, low grade rock phosphate deposits can be utilized provided efficient microorganisms can be harnessed to release the bound phosphates in them³. India has large deposits of rock phosphates estimated at about 140 millions tonnes⁴. Thus, these deposits can be of agronomic importance if they are directly applied to soils with phosphate solubilising microbes commonly referred to as "biofertilizers". Fungi, especially *Aspergillus* sp. are highly effective in this regard, the process being accompanied by the production of extracellular organic acid or hydrolytic enzymes⁴⁻¹⁸.

In the present study an attempt was made to enhance the solubilisation process by adding metal ions and EDTA to the incubation medium. An attempt has also been made to study the role of acid phosphatase and organic acids in the process of dissolution of rock phosphate.

Materials and methods :

Collection of the rock phosphate ore : Samples of rock phosphate ore were obtained from Rajasthan State Mines and Minerals Ltd., Udaipur and crushed in a ball

mill to make fine granules and 200 mesh particles were collected after passing through a sieve. The chemical composition of the rock was – P₂O₅ content 23.64%, SiO₂ and Fe₂O₃ content was 1.21% and 1.36% respectively. Other components were CaO (51.2%), MgO (2.6%) and loss on ignition was 19.9%¹⁹.

Microorganism : A mutant strain of *Aspergillus niger* was developed in our laboratory by using ethyl methane sulfonate (0.05–0.2 M for 2 h) and γ rays (Co⁶⁰ 10–50 K rad). This strain *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ is capable of solubilising 30–35% of 23.64 mg P₂O₅ of rock phosphate. This strain was maintained on Czapek dox agar slants and grown at 30 °C for 7 days for sufficient sporulation and then stored at 4 °C.

Inoculum : The inoculums was prepared by washing the slants with sterile distilled water and filtering the resulting spore suspension through several layers of sterile cotton. The density was adjusted to 12 × 10⁶ spores per ml of the spore suspension. 5% (v/v) of the spore suspension was used as the inoculum.

Medium and cultural conditions : The medium used for the solubilisation of rock phosphate ore consisted of (in %) : NaNO₃ 0.04, KCl 0.1, KH₂PO₄ 0.03 yeast extract 0.1, rock phosphate ore 0.1, with an initial pH of 4.0, 4.0% glucose was separately sterilized and added aseptically to 160 ml of fermentation medium taken in 250 ml conical flasks. Surface culture fermentation was adopted at 28–30 °C for 8 days^{20,21}.

For determining the optimum concentration of metal ions, $ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, $CaCO_3$ and $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ at different concentrations were added to the fermentation medium (FM). The chemically defined medium was made free of metal impurities by the chloroform extraction procedure and the inorganic salt of the mineral was added in graded amounts to determine the optimum concentration at which effective solubilisation occurs²². Ethylenedinitrilotetra acetic acid disodium salt dehydrate (Titriplex® III) was added at 1–6 mg/ml to study its effect on solubilisation. Chemicals for the medium were obtained from Qualigens Excelar and were of analytical grade.

Estimation of phosphorus solubilised : At the end of the incubation period the organism was separated from the fermentation medium by filtering through Whatman No. 40. The fermentation broth was centrifuged at room temperature to yield a clear solution. This was made upto the mark in 250 ml volumetric flasks with double distilled water. Soluble phosphate was determined titrimetrically by taking a fixed volume of the filtrate and precipitating with 10% ammonium molybdate and dissolving in *N*/10 HCl using phenolphthalein as indicator. From the volume of alkali consumed, percentage P_2O_5 was calculated²³.

1 ml (*N*) NaOH = 0.003087 g P_2O_5

All experiments were done in triplicates with corresponding controls and the results were an average of the three.

Preparation of enzymes extract :

Exogenous enzyme measurements : The culture filtrate was collected by passing *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ cultures after 8 days of solubilisation experiment through Whatman No. 40 filter paper. The filtrate was collected in 250 ml volumetric flasks and the volume made upto the mark with double distilled water. Phosphatase activity in culture filtrates was estimated by the method described later.

Endogenous enzyme measurements : The mycelia mat obtained after filtration of 160 ml of fermentation broth was washed with distilled water. The mycelium was pressed dry by hand in cheese cloth and weighed (damp weight). A quantity of quartz sand twice the damp weight of the mycelium was added to the mycelium in a chilled mortar and the mixture ground in the cold for 5 to 10 min. Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer (0.1 *N*, pH 5.4)

was added to extract the solubilised enzymes and the extract centrifuged at 10000 r.p.m. for 15 min in a HIMAC centrifuge at 4 °C. The final supernatant was used as the enzyme source.

Phosphatase assay : The phosphatase activity was measured by using *p*-nitrophenyl phosphate as the substrate and spectrophotometrically estimated the liberated *para*-nitrophenol at 420 nm. Standard curve was drawn with standard *para*-nitrophenol solution of 100 µg/ml. Phosphatase activity was expressed in µmol of *para*-nitrophenol liberated/mm/ml of culture filtrate at 37 °C.

One unit of phosphatase activity is defined as the release of 1.0 µmol of *para*-nitrophenol per minute.

Generally, a 0.1 ml enzyme solution was incubated at 37 °C for 30 min with 2.0 ml buffer (0.1 *N* sodium acetate acetic-acid buffer, pH 5.4) and 0.5 ml *para*-nitrophenyl phosphate (20 mM) which acts as the substrate. The reaction was terminated by adding 1 (*N*) NaOH and absorbance noted at 420 nm. All assays were carried out in duplicates with corresponding controls (without substrate)²⁴.

Estimation of dry cell weight (DCW) : DCW of the spores were determined by the method of Shah *et al.*²⁵.

Statistical analysis : All data were expressed as mean ± SEM, where *n* = 6. The data were analysed by one way ANOVA followed by Dunett's post hoc multiple comparison test using "prism 4.0" software (Graph pad Inc., USA). A "p" value less than 0.05 was considered as significant and less than 0.01 was considered highly significant.

Results and discussion

Effect of various metal ions :

Ferrous sulphate ($FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$) as a source of micro elements was supplemented to the FM at the rate of 1.25 µg/ml. *Aspergillus niger* requires both micro and macro elements for proper growth and metabolism. Iron forms an integral part of the fungal protoplasm and poor growth and poor sporulation occur due to absence of this element²⁵. Fig. 1 shows that maximum solubilisation of 75.56% P_2O_5 was achieved at a concentration of 20.0 µg/ml of the ferrous salt. Acid production was also maximum as related to fall in pH. Acid phosphatase activity was also detectable at a concentration of 20.0 µg/ml.

Zinc ions supplied to the culture medium in the form

Fig. 1. Effect of different concentrations of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on the solubilisation of Indian rock phosphate by *Aspergillus niger* and on its acid phosphatase activity (Values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Fig. 2. Effect of different concentrations of $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on the solubilisation of Indian rock phosphate by *Aspergillus niger* and on its acid phosphatase activity (Values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

of zinc sulphate ($\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) aids fungal growth at very low concentrations²⁵. Higher concentrations of this metal often prove toxic and may even lead to mutagenic changes in the microbe. Adding zinc sulphate caused negligible growth at higher concentrations along with inhibition of fungal solubilisation of rock phosphate (Fig. 2).

Inclusion of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the medium thus gave better results compared to the control i.e. after optimisation of physical and chemical parameters while inclusion of $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ gave highly inhibitory results^{20,21}.

Adding increasing amounts of CaCO_3 (0.5–2.0%) as a source of Ca^{2+} for fungal nutrition made the culture filtrate highly alkaline after 8 days of incubation than the control culture filtrate with no CaCO_3 added. By increasing the concentration of CaCO_3 there was a gradual drop from 64.82% P_2O_5 of control to 21.68% P_2O_5 at 201% CaCO_3 (Fig. 3). As the pH changed more to the alkaline side, acid phosphatase activity was undetected. The role of calcium in fungal nutrition has been well documented²⁷. It is evident from Fig. 3 that CaCO_3 supports growth of the microorganism but does not support phosphorus solubilisation. This is due to less acid production and also

Fig. 3. Effect of varying concentrations of calcium source (CaCO_3) on the solubilisation of Indian rock phosphate by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ and on its acid phosphatase activity (Values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Ca^{2+} recombines with the phosphorous released, thus inhibiting the solubilisation process.

Role of EDTA :

Disodium salt of ethylenediamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) when added at an increasing concentration of 1–6 mg/ml resulted in enhanced solubilisation of phosphorus. Maximum solubilisation (80.46% P_2O_5) was achieved at 2–3 mg/ml (Fig. 4). The solubilisation however reached a plateau when > 3.0 mg/ml EDTA was added. EDTA is a known metal chelator. Phosphorus is present as insoluble Ca, Al or Fe phosphates. EDTA probably acts by the chelation of free Ca^{2+} ions released during dissolution².

Fig. 4. Effect of chelating agent (EDTA) on the solubilisation of Indian rock phosphate by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀ (Values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Conclusion :

Thus, it can be concluded that along with the fermentation medium Fe^{2+} ions and EDTA when added, enhance the agronomic effectiveness of phosphate rock on solubilisation by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀₀. Also, several factors work in conjunction with each other for solubilisation of phosphate rock. Production of hydrolytic enzymes such as acid phosphatase bring about enzymatic dissolution of the rock²⁸. A significant correlation between the amount of acid phosphatase produced and fungal population contributing to the phosphorus pool has been observed²⁹. Organic acid production as evident by a

drop in pH of the FM during the solubilisation process has also been observed^{30,31}. These organic acids have a direct chelating effect on the rock phosphate ore beside contributing to general acidifying effect on the surrounding environment. This acidity also influences the activity of acid phosphatase enzyme.

Further studies are in progress to assess the role of acid phosphatase and purification of the enzyme and its use as an effective tool in the fertilizer industry.

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